

EDEN ISS

D5.2 – NDS Performance Document

prepared for

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Executive summary

From January through to September 2018, the FEG plant production system under the command of Paul Zabel and mission control in Bremen managed to produce 77 kilograms of fresh lettuce, 51 kilograms of cucumbers and 29 kilograms of tomatoes, along with a number of other herbs and leafy greens. As part of a group of interoperating subsystems, the NDS performed as expected in a high density continuous plant production greenhouse. Some problems were encountered, however none that had an impact of operation or plant productivity.

The main points of failure were with fluid and air pumps, however as electrical components with moving parts, this was not unexpected. Lessons learned from this deployment will be adopted and used to enhance system reliability and improve plant productivity in the EDEN-ISS and in future iterations of the technology.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AIT	Assembly Integration and Test	CAB	Bio-regenerative Environmental Control
APH	Advanced Plant Habitat	CAD	Computer Aided Design
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	CDH	Command and Data Handling
ASI	Italian Space Agency	EC	Electrical conductivity
ATS	Analogue Test Site	FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support System	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
C.R.O.P.	Combined Regenerative Organic-food Production	NFT	Nutrient Film Technique

1 System Review

The Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG) section houses eight multi-level growth racks which are scaled to cultivate the selected candidate crops (see EDEN ISS plant selection report). Growth racks held two, four or eight growing trays, depending on the plant species and rack position within the FEG (Figure 1). A total of 42 growing units (positions) providing approximately 11.9 m² of growing area were accommodated within the FEG (Figure 2).

Figure 1: FEG layout showing rack and tray positioning during plant growth.

Figure 2: Future Exploration Greenhouse – Plant tray configuration including illustration of the relevant definitions of chamber, rack, unit, level and tray.

The overall NDS design was based on an existing hydroponic concept developed by DLR Institute of Space Systems that is a hybridization of classic nutrient film technique (NFT) and aeroponics. The system utilizes standard 400 x 600 x 120 mm food grade polypropylene shipping boxes (growing

trays), adapted covers and high pressure misting to achieve an appropriate degree of plant water delivery and root zone oxygenation.

The main component rack (Figure 3) located within the Service Section contained two stainless steel 250 litre nutrient solution tanks and internal primary mixing pumps. Sensors included pH, EC, temperature, water level and water flow status, while manual/semi-automated system disinfection utilized an integrated ozonation system. In order to make maintenance and calibration simpler, pH and EC probes were suspended directly in the nutrient tanks with easy access from above. Stock nutrient reservoirs and acid/base pH control solutions were contained below the main tanks, and the high pressure self-priming delivery pumps were controlled by the Argus Control System. Both nutrient tanks had redundant pH, EC and temperature sensors to ensure system reliability. Each nutrient tank was operated independently and could have different nutrient solution compositions that depended on experiment and plant requirements. Each nutrient tank was supplied by two separate concentrated nutrient supply tanks (traditionally known as A and B, but in this case the second tank had additional solutions labelled C and D to avoid confusion). Both tanks were supplied from the same acid and base reservoirs for pH control. All components in the NDS Service Section rack were placed to allow easy access and simplified maintenance.

Figure 3: Front view of the main NDS rack components within the Service Section.

The main NDS rack fed the growing systems located in the FEG (Figure 4) which contained four growing rack systems on each side of the central corridor. Each rack could be operated/isolated separately as each had separate high pressure primary pumps for delivery to the growing tray misting nozzles. Growing racks consisted of either 8 grow trays (short plants e.g. lettuce, basil, etc.), four grow trays (medium plants, e.g. tomato) or two grow trays (tall plants e.g. cucumber). An additional 8 tray short

plant rack was also available for seedling establishment or additional planting space for short-stature plants. Each of the eight stacks could be fed by either nutrient tank through manually operated 3-way valves on both delivery and nutrient return. The 3-way valves were located in the floor of the FEG and were accessible via removable floor panels. Solution compositional changes do not take place very often, so access through flooring panels was appropriate and helped to alleviate space constraints.

Figure 4: EDEN ISS top view showing the FEG section on the left and the main service section on the right.

Return of the nutrient feed stream from the growing tray was by a combination of gravity return to a central lower reservoir (Figure 5) and active pumping with submersible pumps which engage in response to water level sensors located within the sump reservoir (Figure 5 – sump pump). The entire NDS solution loop was closed (recirculating). Water lost to evaporation and transpiration was recovered by the condenser located in the Atmosphere Management System rack in the Service Section. Recovered water was directed to the fresh water tank located in the floor of the airlock. Additional water from the fresh water tank was injected into the nutrient tanks in response to the predetermined tank water level, or as required for nutrient composition control (i.e. to lower EC). A cooling loop was included in the nutrient tank design, but was not utilized.

Figure 5: Under-floor layout of the NDS supply and return piping.

The overall final NDS system design as deployed in Antarctica for the first test mission is shown in the block diagram (Figure 6). Complete details of the system can be found in the EDEN ISS-WP3.2-D3.5-NDS Design Document.

Figure 6: Block diagram showing system flow and components of the NDS.

EDEN ISS
Nutrient Delivery System Layout
Revision R 03/27/2019

Note: GFCI required for all electrical components supplied by mains power. System to comply with IEC 60364

2 System Performance

During the Antarctic deployment from January through to September 2018, the relatively small footprint FEG plant production system managed to produce an astounding 77 kilograms of fresh lettuce, 51 kilograms of cucumbers and 29 kilograms of tomatoes, along with a number of other herbs and leafy greens. As a general rule, the plants themselves are the best indicators of system performance and production success or failure, and in this case, plant production was successful. A handful of operational problems arose over the course of testing, but none of these were unusual or unexpected in a high density crop production system. Lessons learned from the first mission deployment will be adopted and used to enhance system reliability and improve plant productivity in the EDEN-ISS Mobile Test Facility and in future iterations of the technology.

There are only two main points of control for the NDS, pH and EC. Both of these operated as expected throughout the first season of plant production. The only deviations from control requirements resulted from operational issues (e.g. filters clogged, tank maintenance and refilling, etc.).

After the initial setup and testing of the growing systems in the beginning thirty days of operation, pH control was excellent. Any deviations from the setpoint were due to easily diagnosed technical issues (broken connectors on the acid delivery supply lines) and pH was never beyond a level suitable for plant growth (Figure 7). Tank 1 followed a higher control level than that of tanks 2, and this was due to a programmed offset within the control software. Tank 1 averaged pH 6.06 +/- 0.18 and tank 2 averaged 5.91 +/- 0.12 over the entire growing period.

Figure 7: pH control in the two nutrient tanks located in the control section of the EDEN container. The red line shows the control level as programmed in the Argus system.

EC monitoring results were similar to that of pH. Control was excellent after the initial thirty day set-up period (Figure). Each nutrient tank had a different EC setpoint, and control was tight with $2.21 \pm 0.13 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$ and $3.49 \pm 0.17 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$ in tanks 1 and 2 respectively. The larger deviations either above or below the setpoint were the result of tank solution changes, maintenance or operational issues. At no time did EC deviate outside of a range amenable to plant growth and productivity.

Figure 8: EC control in the two nutrient tanks located in the control section of the EDEN container. The red lines show the control level as programmed in the Argus system.

Also monitored but not controlled was the nutrient solution temperature in the main nutrient tanks (Figure 9). Tank temperature followed that of the well-controlled room temperature and was quite stable with 19.90 +/- 0.74°C in tank 1 and 19.97 +/- 0.78°C in tank 2.

Figure 9: Temperature in NDS nutrient tanks 1 and two over the course of the growing season in the EDEN-ISS container. The light red line shows the FEG temperature while the green line is the outdoor temperature.

As indicated above, the best evidence of a properly functioning plant production system is found in the healthy growth and productivity of the crops produced (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Young plants and plants ready for harvest in Antarctica.

3 System Maintenance and Observed Issues

In a system as complex as the EDEN-ISS, some operational and maintenance issues will certainly arise during long-term operation. Most of the problems encountered were minor and can be accounted for in future iterations of the technology. The log of NDS related tasks and issues is presented in ‘Appendix 1. Work report compilation of NDS system entries’ and problems encountered are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Problems encountered in the NDS system during operation.

Days since start	Problem encountered	Solution implemented
24	Fresh water tank circulation pump clogged	Filter cleaned
28	Uneven stock solution (A vs. B) use	Feed line not submerged in stock tank A
56	EC sensors not reading the same	Calibration of EC sensors
63	Two HP pump not delivering due to clogged main filter	Cleaned main filter
66	Noisy air pump tank 1	Replaced pump
88	Sump pump high level alarm due to failed level switch	Replaced level switch
96	Bubbles on air stone stopped working on tank 1	Replaced air stone
112	Noisy air pump tank 2	Pump replaced
114	FEG leak sensor broken	unknown
143	Air pumps failure	Replaced pumps
144	HP pump failure	Replaced pump
149	NDS main filters clogged	Clean filters
149	Tubing connector on acid pump failure	Replace connector
150	Ozone generator failure	Replace generator
154	Tubing connector on acid pump failure	Replace connector
164	Circulation pump 1 flow sensor failure	Future repair
202	High pressure pump failure – internal short	Replaced
210	Leak sensor failure	Overridden
228	High pressure pump failure	Replaced
231	Sump pump 1 level sensor failure	Changed Argus control method to compensate

The problems noted above were not unexpected, as a continuously operating plant hydroponics system will have pumps fail and filters clog from time to time. Filter clogging could be reduced dramati-

cally through routine maintenance, and this was proposed prior to deployment (Figure 9: Maintenance schedule as outlined in the final design document for the NDS.). The busy schedule on the ground meant some maintenance requirements were not always covered, however even with these problems, plant productivity was not jeopardized.

Task ¹	Maintenance Interval					
	daily	weekly	monthly	quarterly	yearly	other
pH/EC sensor calibration			X			Or when verification test does not agree with sensor reading
pH/EC sensor validation	X					
NDS system cleaning						Before each experiment or when contamination is suspected/confirmed
Exterior cleaning			X			
Stock tank cleaning					X	Also between changes in stock composition
NDS main filter		X				
Misting nozzles			X			Also during general tray maintenance after plant harvest
Inspect tray drains	X					
Tray cleaning						Before each planting and/or according to horticultural management procedures
Pinch valve tubing inspection/repositioning		X				See note in design lessons learned section

¹Task procedures are noted below

Figure 9: Maintenance schedule as outlined in the final design document for the NDS.

The early failure of the air pumps was likely due to incompatibility of the pump with gaseous ozone. Ozone is a strong oxidizer that spares very few plastics, so care in selection of the wetted components is paramount. Similarly with connector failures on the acid injection system, many plastics and metals are incompatible with acid and even just one incorrect component can cause system failure, as was the case here. Fortunately these failures were minimal and did not compromise plant production as they could be addressed in a timely manner. As with most sub-systems, due to sensors which monitor vital functions such as leak detection and pressure sensors, the Argus control system was able to announce a problem and provide temporary measures to mitigate crop failure. Lessons learned from this deployment will be incorporated into future control algorithms in order to improve alarm response and error checking.

4 On-Site System Improvements

During the first deployment, only three minor changes to the NDS system were made:

- The growing trays were angled towards the drains in order to allow better flow inside the trays.
- Large labels were added to the front of each tray to be used as reference for the images taken by the observation cameras.
- The ozone “on time” was increased to improve effectiveness of ozonation on nutrient solution microbial abatement.

After the first season was complete, the DLR team returned to the research station to make further upgrades to the FEG, with specific changes to the NDS that included:

- Replacement of (part of) the rockwool holders with an updated design which provided a better seal to the tray lids, preventing nutrient solution from seeping through and hopefully reducing microbial growth around the rockwool holders. Additionally, the new design should be less fragile.

Figure 10. New rockwool plug holder design.

- Replacement of the stock solution bottles with larger bottles that included integrated level sensors and micro-circulation pumps. The second season of operation will see the overwinter crew tend to the garden, and these modifications will reduce the number of times that the stock tanks need to be replenished. The level sensor will allow mission control to observe nutrient use and request solution changes when required. The addition of micro-pumps within the stock tanks will allow the use of pre-packaged salt mixtures. The micro-pumps decrease the chance of nutrient precipitation.

Figure 11. New larger stock and acid/base bottles.

- Instead of having a dedicated pump for each individual rack, racks R1+R2 and R3+R4 were combined to be on the same pump. The unused pumps remain in the system for use as spares in case of pump failure.
- An additional level was added to L4 and it was integrated into the NDS feed and drain lines. This reduced the number of nursery/germination trays available.
- The air pumps that deliver ozone to the NDS tank were replaced with similar pumps (KNF) but with internal gaskets and diaphragms that can withstand ozone.
- Connectors associated with acid and base delivery were replaced with connectors made of Teflon.

5 Proposed Future System Improvements

Although pump failures and filter clogging are the modest cost in the continuous operation of a plant production system, improvements can be made that decrease complexity and the number of moving parts that are points of failure. To reduce system complexity, the following recommendations are proposed.

5.1 *Set nutrient tanks into the floor*

The current system has the main nutrient tanks positioned above the lowest level of the growing boxes. This necessitates the need for a sump pump to return nutrient solution back to the tanks after delivery to the plants. The simplest system for nutrient delivery involves pumping to the plant system with gravity return of solution back to the main tank, or alternatively, gravity delivery of nutrient solution to the plants with a pumped return to the tank. With the nutrient tanks in the floor within the FEG, the requirement for a sump return tank and pump is removed. As the loss of this return pumping system shuts down nutrient delivery completely, its removal takes away one major possible failure point.

As an additional benefit, a tank located in the FEG floor would be shallower and the need for an air pump and air stone to move ozone or oxygen into the nutrient tank would not be required. The lower depth would allow the use of a siphon draw on the recirculating pump already located in the tank.

5.2 *Remove valved distribution system*

The current system that allows switching between tank 1 and tank 2 nutrient solution is overly complicated and not necessarily required. Solution modification within the tanks, if needed, can be accomplished through software control and use of modified stock solutions. A two tank system should still be employed for redundancy and to accommodate the nutritional requirements of different crop species. Each side of the FEG would take feed and return from a separate tank. This would save considerably on hardware and maintenance. System cleaning would be greatly simplified and places for bacteria to accumulate would be eliminated.

5.3 *Reduction in high pressure pump count*

The eight pumps used in the current system are excessive and can easily be reduced to one pump per tank with the addition of a suitably sized expansion tank. An expansion tank reduces pumping on/off cycles by filling a pressurized reservoir in order to maintain a constant line pressure. This change would require the addition of eight solenoid valves which would then distribute the nutrient solution on demand. For redundancy, two pumps (main plus back-up) would be used to reduce or eliminate down time in the case of pump failure. Using solenoid valves instead of high pressure pumps will also reduce power requirements for the NDS.

5.4 *Aqueous ozone sensor*

The addition of an aqueous ozone sensor to the nutrient tanks would allow monitoring and precise control of ozone in solution. An optimized aqueous ozone concentration would increase the effectiveness of control in the destruction of bacteria which lead to the formation of biofilms on wetted surfaces.

A simplified NDS block diagram with these modifications is shown in Figure 12.

Note: GFCI required for all electrical components supplied by mains power. System to comply with IEC 60364

NOTE: RO water system at Neumayer Station III

EDEN ISS
Nutrient Delivery System (NEW) Layout
Revision a 03/31/2019

Figure 12: Modified block diagram showing changes involved in a floor based nutrient tank.

References

Appendix 1. Work report compilation of NDS system entries

Date	Day	Tasks completed	Observations/Off-nominal Events
26.02.2018	0	- RO water transport to MTF - Wastewater transport from MTF to station - Preparation of nutrient solution in NDS tanks - Setup of NDS control	
28.02.2018	2	- RO water transport to MTF (100 liters by hand)	
01.03.2018	3	- Preparation of nutrient stock solution, 8x 4 liter bottles	
12.03.2018	15		- FW tank almost depleted. Alarm went on.
19.03.2018	22	- Exchange/refill of stock nutrient solution bottles in NDS rack. Solution 1 and 2.	
22.03.2018	24	- Cleaning of FW tank circulation pump, exchange of filter	- WW tank ~50% - FW ~30% - Filter of FW tank circulation pump clogged with slime
26.03.2018	28	- Ozone sensor fixed - Ozone sensor placed inside NDS rack	- Volume in stock solution A of tank 2 ~ twice as much as solution B. Air bubbles in tube. → Feed line not properly placed inside the bottle → Dosing pump C turned on manually until volume in both stock solutions was equal again.
28.03.2018	30		- Stock solution bottles tank 1 and tank 2 below ~20%
30.03.2018	32	- Stock solution bottles exchanged on NDS tank 2	
31.03.2018	33	- Stock solution preparation (1x each A+B leafy and fruity) - Stock solution bottles exchanged on NDS tank 1	
04.04.2018	37	- 1x oxygen tab in FW tank	
06.04.2018	39	- Acid bottle exchanged in NDS	
07.04.2018	40	- Stock solution bottles exchanged on NDS tank 2	
13.04.2018	46	- Mixing of nutrient stock solution bottles, 2 each, 8 in total - Exchange of nutrient stock solution bottles of NDS tank 1	
14.04.2018	47	- Mixing of micro nutrient stock bottles, 1 each	
16.04.2018	49	- Exchange of stock solution bottles of NDS tank 2	
18.04.2018	51	- Fresh water tank refilled - Waste water tank emptied	
20.04.2018	53	- Daily system and plant check - ISPR thermocouple testing with Marco - Video chat with Bremen	
23.04.2018	56		- EC sensors of NDS tank 2 deviate by around 0.4 mS.

25.04.2018	58	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exchange of stock solution bottles NDS tank 1 and tank 2 - Cleaning of sump pump 1 and 2 box and filter and drain pipes - Cleaning of NDS feed line 1 and 2 filters - Moved tubes in pinch valve 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sump pump 1 more dirty than sump pump 2.
26.04.2018	59	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calibration of NDS sensors in tank 1 and 2, pH and EC probes. 	
29.04.2018	62	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FW tank fill-up 	
30.04.2018	63	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixing of stock solution bottles (2x each A and B) - Emptying of NDS tank 2 - Filling of NDS tank 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pump R3 had high pressure (>10 bar for couple of cycles), but is back to normal. - Pump R4 pressure sensor shows 0 bar when active since around 17:00. Pump turned manually off. Check scheduled for next day.
01.05.2018	64		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pump R3 low pressure alarm at around 07:00 in the morning. Pump was turned off manually to prevent damage. -> Filter of NDS feed line 2 below the tank was clogged with slime. Probably the refill of the tank the day before washed a lot of slime into the filter. The tank was wiped with paper tissues before refill. Next refill the tank needs to be cleaned more thoroughly and the filter needs to be checked after refill. ->> Because of the pumps being turned off, but the light kept on, the plants in R3 and R4 suffered and the leaves were hanging down when entering the FEG at around 10:30. Pumps R3 and R4 were turned on for 5 minute intervals manually throughout the day to provide the plants with extra amounts of fluid. Kohlrabi in R4 and Cucumbers in R3 recovered until the evening. Tomato plants in R4 still look not good, but the leaves close to the bottom already show signs of recovery.
03.05.2018	66		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air pump1 really noisy. Louder than normal.
06.05.2018	69	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixing of 2x each fruity stock solution bottles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visit of MTF not possible due to weather.
07.05.2018	70	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filter of circulation pump in FW tank exchanged - O2 tab in FW tank - Refill of fresh water tank - Stock solution bottles of NDS tank 1 and tank 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wastewater tank full. - Air pump 1 turned off (around 11:00), because of loud noise. Need to be exchanged with spare part. - Ozone generator activation time

		2 exchanged	reduced from 30 minutes to 15 minutes per activation so that tank 2 is not flooded with too much ozone.
12.05.2018	75	- Waste water tank emptied	
13.05.2018	76	- Exchange of NDS acid stock bottle - Exchange of NDS tank 1 stock solution bottles - Air pump of NDS tank 1 exchanged with spare part	
14.05.2018	77	- Dumping of waste water	
18.05.2018	81	- Mixing of nutrient stock solution bottles 2x each leafy, 1x each fruity	
21.05.2018	84	- Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2	
25.05.2018	88	-	- Sump pump R high level und FEG leakage sensor alarm at around 23:50. -> High-pressure pumps and LED lamps turned off for the night.
26.05.2018	89	- Exchange of broken level switch with spare part	- Alarms of previous night caused by a failure of the level switch inside the right sump pump box.
28.05.2018	91	- Exchange stock solution bottles NDS tank 1 - Exchange of stock solution bottles NDS tank 2	
30.05.2018	93	- Fresh water tank filled up	
02.06.2018	96	- Mixing stock solution bottles 1x each leafy, 2x each fruity	- Bubble stone in NDS tank 1 probably clogged. -> exchange
05.06.2018	99	- Stock solution bottles exchanged in NDS tank 2	
12.06.2018	106	- Mixing of 1x diluted acid 4 L bottle - Exchange of acid bottle in NDS	
15.06.2018	109	- Mixing of nutrient stock solution 1x each leafy and fruity, A and B - Mixing of 1x diluted acid 4 L bottle	
18.06.2016	112	- Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2	- Air pump 2 very noisy. - NDS dosing pump alarms on tank 2 not working.
19.06.2018	113	- Emptying of NDS tank 1 - Cleaning of NDS tank 1 and submersed equipment - Cleaning of sump pump 1 (left) - Cleaning of NDS tank 1 outlet filter - Filling of NDS tank 1 - Exchange of nutrient stock solution bottles on NDS tank 1	- Waste water tank full.
20.06.2018	114	- Waste water tank emptied	- Leak sensor FEG broken.
22.06.2018	116	- Mixing of nutrient stock solution bottles 2x each fruity, 1x each leafy	
23.06.2018	117	- Exchange of acid bottle in NDS - Emptying of NDS tank 2 - Cleaning of NDS tank 2 and submersed	- Fresh water tank level low

		<p>equipment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cleaning of sump pump 2 (right) - Cleaning of NDS tank 2 outlet filter - Filling of NDS tank 2 	
25.06.2018	119	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Refilling of fresh water tank - Exchange of fresh water tank circulation pump filter - Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 1 	
27.06.2018	121	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixing of micronutrients leafy and fruity 1x 1L each - Mixing of nutrient stock solution bottles 2x each leafy, 1x each fruity 	
04.07.2018	128	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2 	
19.07.2018	143	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixing of 1x 4L NDS acid bottle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Both NDS air pumps and/or bubble stone not working correctly -> no air supply for the nutrient solution; ozone generator turned off manually
20.07.2018	144	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fresh water tank refilling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste water tank full - L3-1 misters deliver less water than normal -> Pump duration for L3 increased from 30 seconds to 60 seconds per interval, check misters
21.07.2018	145	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Daily system and plant check - Emptying of waste water tank 	
23.07.2018	147	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exchange of NDS acid bottle - Mixing of nutrient stock solution bottles 2x each leafy and fruity A+B 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Misters in L3-1 OK, but high-pressure pump L3 is very quiet compared to other pumps and pressure at misters is low ->> pump need to be exchanged with spare part
24.07.2018	148	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work on NDS air pumps - Cleaning of bubble stones 	
25.07.2018	149	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cleaning of NDS supply line filters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NDS supply line filter of tank 1 clogged completely. After cleaning high-pressure pump L3 supplied normal amount of water again - Tube connector on outlet of acid dosing pump broken. Tube got lose and around one full 4 L bottle of diluted acid was spilled inside the NDS rack
26.07.2018	150	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acid pump outlet fixed - Mixing of 2x 4 L diluted acid bottles - Setting up of new air pump mounting, NDS air pumps running again 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ozone generator does not produce enough ozone anymore, see separate mail
30.07.2018	154	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exchange of ozone generator 'cell' - Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 1 and tank 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Second connector on NDS acid pump also broken.
31.07.2018	155	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acid pump inlet fixed 	

02.08.2018	157	- Calibration of pH and EC sensors on NDS tank1 and tank 2	
09.08.2018	164	- Cleaning of NDS tank 2 circulation tank flow sensor -> sensor clean, but still no signal. Probably sensor or wire broken.	
15.08.2018	170	- Fresh water tank refill	
17.08.2018	172	- Mixing of stock solution bottles (2x each A+B leafy and fruity)	- New fruity stock solution with reduced KNO3 and increased Ca2NO3.
19.08.2018	174		
22.08.2018	177	- Exchange stock solution bottles NDS tank 1 and tank 2 - Exchange of acid bottle in NDS	
23.08.2018	178	- Dosing pump test with long tube	
28.08.2018	183	- Waste water tank emptied	
31.08.2018	186	- Exchange of stock solution bottle on NDS tank 1 and tank 2	
02.09.2018	188	- Mixing of stock solution bottles (2x leafy A and 2x fruity A)	
03.09.2018	189	- Exchange of base bottle in NDS - Emptying of NDS tank 2 - Cleaning of NDS tank 2 and submersed equipment - Cleaning of NDS tank 2 outlet filter - Mixing of stock solution bottles (2x leafy B and 2x fruity B)	
14.09.2018	200	- Mixing of nutrient stock solutions (1x each leafy A+B, 2x each fruity A+B)	
16.09.2018	202		- High-pressure pump L2 broken. -> caused the triggering of the FI switch for the NDS FEG section of the power distribution system at around 20:10. Consequently all other high-pressure pumps and the two sump pumps went off. ->> Illumination system switched to visitor mode. Watering of plants stopped in Argus. Visit of the MTF and check of the power box confirmed that FI was triggered and cause by failure of pump L2. All pumps except L2 were turned on again. Illumination system remained in visitor mode until morning the next day at around 10:30.
17.09.2018	203	- L2 pump (broken) exchanged with spare part	
18.09.2018	204	- Refilling of fresh water tank - Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2	
19.09.2018	205	- Emptying of NDS tank 1 - Cleaning of NDS tank 1 and submersed equipment - Cleaning of NDS tank 2 outlet filter	

		- Filling of NDS tank 1	
20.09.2018	206	- Cleaning of NDS bubble stones	
21.09.2018	207		- Air pump 2 removed from system for maintenance
24.09.2018	210	- NDS/CDH malfunction fix (see right column)	- Schedule of high-pressure pump R3 changed from 00:00:30/00:05:30 to 00:01:00/00:05:00 (on/off) - SES leak sensor malfunction. Triggered since Friday 21.09.2018 around 22:00. -> FW pump, recirculation pumps in NDS tanks, FW solenoids shut down due to override. ->> Tank level of NDS tanks falling. FW tank got filled to almost maximum level, due to condensate recovery. ->>> Overrides when leak sensors are active disabled for FW pump, recirculation pumps and solenoids
26.09.2018	212	- Exchange of nutrient stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2	- Tubing in NDS acid bottle curled up above fluid level. -> no acid could be pumped. Probably already since Monday.
27.09.2018	213	- Mixing of 2x each A+B leafy and fruity	
01.10.2018	217	- Exchange of NDS acid bottle - Exchange of NDS stock solution bottles on tank 1	
08.10.2018	224	- Air pump 2 reinstalled	
09.10.2018	225	- Emptying of waste water tank	
10.10.2018	226	- Exchange of nutrient stock solution on NDS tank 1 and tank 2	
12.10.2018	228		- High-pressure pump R1 broken around 22:15 -> FI of NDS FEG triggered => all high-pressure pumps and sump pumps off.
13.10.2018	229	- Exchange of pump R1 with spare part	
15.10.2018	231	- Fresh water tank refilling	- Sump pump 1 (left) high level alarm around 11:10. -> Level switch not working properly. Pump only on for a fraction of a second when water level reached. ->> Level switch exchanged with spare part.
18.10.2018	234	- Mixing of NDS acid bottle - Mixing of NDS base bottle - Mixing of NDS stock solution bottles (2x each leafy A/B, 1x each fruity A/B)	
21.10.2018	237	- Exchange of NDS stock solution bottles on tank 1 and tank 2	- Sump pump 1 (left) high level alarm around 15:00. -> Level switch not working. No more spare parts. ->> High-pressure pumps turned

			offline, LEDs turned offline.
22.10.2018	238		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bypass for sump pump 1 control. Sump pump relay connected to Argus box. Level switch disconnected from sump pump. Sump is now controlled through a timer function in Argus. Initial schedule every 5 minutes for 6 seconds. - Error messages and alarms in Argus. (e.g. false sensor readings of sump pump high level sensors and NDS tank level sensors. -> Caused by the malfunctioning leak sensors sending to high voltage signals to the I/O module. ->> Leak sensors disconnected from the I/O module inside the Argus box.
23.10.2018	239		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sump pump 1 not working. Probably since 00:20. ->> Fuse inside power box was triggered. Nominal operation started again 11:15.
24.10.2018	240		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adjusting of sump pump 1/left timer settings in Argus. L4 pump schedule adjusted from every 01:00:00 for 60 seconds to every 00:30:00 for 30 seconds. - Fuse inside power box was triggered late afternoon 23.10. Nominal operation started again around 10:00. -> Fuse exchanged inside power box.
29.10.2018	245	- Exchange of NDS acid bottle	
02.11.2018	249	- Exchange of stock solution bottles on NDS tank 1 and tank 2	
05.11.2018	252	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixing of NDS stock solution bottles 2x each A+B leafy and fruity - Mixing of leafy micronutrients bottle 	
07.11.2018	254	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New level switch implemented in sump pump 1/left, sump pump timer on manual on - High-pressure pump R1 removed (probably damaged), exchanged with pump L4 -> no pump connected to watered nursery 	
11.11.2018	258	- Exchange of nutrient stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2	
14.11.2018	262	- Exchange of nutrient stock solution bottles on NDS tank 1	
16.11.2018	264	- Exchanged of nutrient stock solution bottles on NDS tank 2	
20.11.2018	268	- NDS high-pressure pumps and dosing pumps manual off	
24.11.2018	272	- Mixing of nutrient stock solution bottles (1x	

		A/B leafy, 2x A/B fruity)	
25.11.2018	273	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Emptying of NDS tank 1- Cleaning NDS tank 1- Emptying of NDS tank 2- Cleaning NDS tank 2- Emptying of waste water tank- Emptying of fresh water tank- Filling of fresh water tank- Exchange of filter of fresh water tank circulation pump- Start filling of NDS tanks, 20 L RO water and around 1,5 stock solution bottles per tank	